

*PIE *Heh₃s (ash tree) is the source of Proto-Germanic *askō “ash, ashes” in the sense of “that which is left behind after fire burns something”: And *k^wetwóres probably comes from the earlier meanings “birch tree; axis mundi; pole; stone; the Cygnus constellation, the Northern Cross”; and the Dithur- of Dithurambos is from *k^wetwóres=“pole of wood”*

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I have come to the conclusion that *Heh₃s the PIE root of “ash (tree)” meant primarily “pointed; to prick, to goad, to drive/to set in motion” and was an old Pre-PIE variant of PIE *h₂eḱs- “axis, axle”, which is also from “to drive, to set in motion” in turn from “to goad, to prick” from “pointed, sharp” (and PIE *h₂eǵ- “to drive” is another variant, and also originally derives from “to prick” from “pointed, sharp”). The World-Tree/Axis Mundi in Norse myth was an ash tree named Yggdrasil, so my proposal that PIE *Heh₃s (the source of “ash (tree)”) is a variant of PIE *h₂eḱs- “axis, axle”, makes a lot of sense, to say the least.

The Axis Mundi rotated the apparent cyclical movement of the constellations in the night-sky, and the Axis Mundi was located in the far north: it is the North Pole. And the Axis Mundi was believed to be set in motion/driven by a higher power, by a deity or a set of deities.

From PIE *Heh₃s derives Proto-Germanic *askaz (which means “ash tree”), as is already known. But in Indo-European linguistics, it has long been a debate about what PIE root if any is the source of Proto-Germanic *askō which referred to “ash, ashes” in the sense of that which is left behind after fire burns something (and the English word “ash, ashes” in this sense derives from Proto-Germanic *askō, as is known). No one apparently has thought to derive it from PIE *Heh₃s, because they did not know the earlier meanings that give rise to the meaning “ash tree”, and which provide a source for the meaning of Proto-Germanic *askō.

I have come to the conclusion that from PIE *Heh₃s also derives Proto-Germanic *askō meaning “ash/ashes (in the sense of that which is left behind after fire burns something)” for three reasons at least:

1) because the ash tree was a tree so often used to make the drill part of the bow-drill: in a Norse myth, the first man is named Ask (known to be cognate to Old Norse Ask=“ash tree”) and the first woman is named Embla, which is already posited to likely have meant “vine” and referred to soft/softish vinewood into which the harder ashwood-drill drills to make by friction a bit of “coal” that is used to make fire. In Indo-European societies and Non-IE societies, an analogy is derived from the drilling of fire and sexual intercourse.

Vines were used as a flammable wood, where they were placed beneath a drill made of harder wood, resulting in fire.

So, that bit of ashy “coal” that is produced from drilling using a wooden bow-drill would have easily led to a word for “ash/ashes” (in the sense of that which is left behind after fire burns something).

2) words for ashes/ash often derive from the meaning “bitter” because ashes taste very bitter, and words for bitter in turn often derive from “sharp, pointed” (sometimes instead bitter derives from “to bite” as in English where “bitter” is cognate with “bite” as in “to bite”: and biting suggests pointed fangs stabbing into the skin). As described above, I posited that “sharp, pointed” was the oldest root-meaning of PIE *Heh₃s.

3) before the meaning “ash tree”, the older meaning of PIE *Heh₃s was probably “birch” tree, a tree that has white bark: and words for birch trees are known to often shift to ash trees, and vice versa. So the main impetus could have been naming “ash, ashes (that which is left behind by fire)” for the white color of the birch tree, a tree that was identified with the Axis Pole of the world and with the stick of the bow-drill, which was probably often made of birch wood as well.

4) because the root-meaning of PIE *Heh₃s was “pointed; to prick, to goad”, and such meanings are known to give rise to the meanings “to drive”, “to propel”, “to throw”, “to cast” (both “pointed” and “to throw” led to the meaning “spear”: ash trees were a very go-to source of spear-wood; and in Old English *æsc* meant “spear” as well as “ash tree”; and in Latin *ornus* means “mountain ash tree” and “spear/lance”, while *fraxinus* in Latin means “ash tree” and “javelin/spear made of ash wood”): and in many cases, words for ash/ashes (in the sense of that which is left behind after fire burns something) come from the earlier meanings “that which is blown around by a puff of air or by a breeze or by a wind-gust”: so the meaning “ash/ashes” could have come from “that which is thrown around, cast around, propelled about” by a puff of air, by a breeze, by a gust of wind. But notice that this root didn’t give rise to words meaning “dust”, “powder” and “chaff”: so reason 4 cannot be the sole reason, but it could have been an additional impetus, but not the primary impetus, which would be either reason 1 or 2 or 3 described above.

In a Norse myth, the three Norns cover the Yggdrasil World-Tree with water from their well under the tree, as well as covering it with *Aur*, which in the myth is a white “clay”, a white “mud” which I think is actually white ash left over from the burning of the Titans (the Titans were turned to ash after being burnt by the thunderbolts of Zeus in one version of the myth between Zeus/the Olympians and the Titans) and from the burning of former worlds/former universes. I agree with the classical scholar Jane Harrison (1850–1828) that Ancient Greek *Τῑτᾶν* (Titan) derives from *τίτᾶνος / τέτᾶνος* meaning “a kind of white earth (probably gypsum); chalk; lime”. I conclude that they used the word *Aur* in the Norse myth because the idea was not that the ashes of the former world were applied directly unmixed, but instead that the white clay/white mud was composed of that ash mixed with a cosmic water: Old Norse *Aur* derives from Proto-Germanic **auraz* meaning “wet sand, wet earth; mud” and “liquid, water, sea”: the older meanings of **auraz* are the meanings without soil, only water.

A mythologist named Christopher Johnsen whom I exchange mythology information with often since 2023 thinks that the “white clay/white mud” of this Norse myth referred to some white paste that he says was made from the white sticky berries of the mistletoe plant; but though I agree that the white clay/white mud of Norse myth could have been associated with the mistletoe, I told him as I tell my readers here that I do not think that mistletoe was the primary and real reference at all, instead I think the white mud/white clay is what I describe above: the ashes of the Titans and of former worlds, burned as this world too is figuratively believed to someday burn away, and from those ashes a new tree (a new universe) will arise.

I agree with R. Gordon Wasson's suggestion that the Birch tree may have been the original tree believed to be the Axis Mundi in many northern Eurasian cultures at least; the ash tree and birch tree are very similar: and words for "birch" and "ash tree" often shift in meaning from one tree to another: but the birch actually has white bark, so the birch tree fits better in that aspect at least.

A.G., 2023 to February 1st 2024

Part 2: *k^wetwóres probably meant "birch tree; axis mundi; pole; stone; the Cygnus constellation, the Northern Cross"

I have been working on the earlier meaning(s) of PIE *k^wetwóres---which in Proto-Indo-European is so far known only to have meant "four"---since 2019 or 2020. My first theory published in December 2020 or January 2021 was that *k^wetwóres- derives from a stem *k^wetu- or *k^wet-, which meant "pointed, sharp": I didn't know it at the time, but that actually would fit (see my discussion of PIE*Heh₃s above) my new theory (as of early February 2024) that *k^wet/*k^wetu is a variant of PIE *g^wet/*g^wétu which means "birch tree; resin; gum".

In the case of *k^wetwóres a possible root-meaning of "pointed" remains possible; a study of the material also leads me to the theory that I first published in the early summer of 2023 (in the 2023 edition of my translation of the Moesian-Thracian Kjolmen inscription) that *k^wetwóres meant "firm, hard, strong, thick", referring to the firm, strong pole of the Axis Mundi, the World-Tree, which, it is now apparent, was conceived of as a birch tree/identified with the birch tree, as we shall see in this paper (the acclaimed R. Gordon Wasson proposed decades ago that the World-Tree/Axis tree of many northern Eurasian cultures, at least, was originally the birch tree).

The birch tree as the Axis Mundi was associated with the Cygnus constellation (the Swan constellation, which is also known as the Northern Cross) and with swans themselves.

Let us read this quote:

"Worldwide in many mythologies, Cygnus was seen as the entrance and exit to the sky-world and perhaps the original location of heaven. The extreme north was where the dead went in the afterlife and they reached it by going to the Pole Star along the north-south meridian line, which splits the heavens in two along its longitudinal zenith. This cosmic axis of the Northern Hemisphere was seen as linked with the axis mundi of the terrestrial world, via a sky-pole, which has featured extensively in shamanic practices across Europe and Asia.

"The Tungus reindeer shamans of Siberia constructed sky-poles topped by swans, up which they would climb in order to reach the sky-world. The Sami shamans in the far North of Sweden, Norway and Finland also practiced similar shamanism where they would dry the Amanita muscaria mushrooms on strings over the hearth and they would enter and exit their dwellings via these cosmic birch poles

(progenitors of Santa Claus)¹. The shaman would enter a trance state and rise up the axis mundi, represented by the birch pole and enter the Milky Way via Cygnus a few hours before dawn.

“ Cygnus was at the northern celestial pole from 16,000-13,000 BC, and is shown in Paleolithic cave art as early as 15,000 BCE as a bird on a pole in the painting of the Dead Man at Lascaux cave.”²

I really recommend taking a look at the website from where I quoted those paragraphs, because on that webpage is shown a photograph of very high (birch?) poles topped with wooden swans, swans that are laid out very much in the form of a cross (+): and I am certain that there (and in the cross shape of the Cygnus constellation) we have the progression from **k^wetwóres* hypothetically (as I posit here) meaning “birch tree; axis pole; the north pole; firm; strong” to meaning “four” and “stone”, as attested in Indo-European languages.

In a paper of mine from December 2020 or January 2021 where I first began publishing about the etymology of **k^wetwóres*, I posited that the root-meaning of **k^wet/*k^wetu* was “pointed, sharp” and I posited that **k^wetwóres* is the source³ of Ancient Greek πέτρᾱ meaning “rock formation: cliff, ledge, cave, ridge; stone as a material (for buildings, statues, etc.)” and πέτρος meaning “rock, stone, boulder”. In that work and in later editions, as well as in the first editions of my work on the Kjolmen inscription, I posited that “pointed, sharp” shifted to “stone” because stones were so often shaped to have sharp points, and used to cut and stab in the stone ages especially. And I cited Iranic “asan” meaning “stone” and deriving from PIE **h₂ek-* “sharp”⁴.

It may be that the root-meaning was “pointed, sharp” and from there developed “stone” and “Axle, Axis”, as we see with PIE **h₂éks*, “axis, axle” developing from PIE **h₂ek-* “sharp, pointed”, or from PIE **h₂eǵ-s-*; in either case, because “sharp, pointed” led to “to prick, to goad>to drive, to set in motion>axis, axle (that which sets in motion the other parts)”, and from “Axis tree/birch tree”, via the very ancient association with the Northern Cross/Cygnus constellation, developed the meaning “four”. From “pointed” could also have developed “to flow”, since “pointed; to prick, to goad” easily leads to “to set in motion; to move; to flow, to run”, and “to flow” could refer to resin-sap flowing from the birch tree.

Or it may be that the root-meaning was “strong, firm; thick, fat”, as I argue those are the original Pre-PIE meanings of PIE **peh₂ǵ-* “to fasten, to make firm; to bring firmly together; to fix something in place”, the source of Latin palus meaning “stake, pole”. So from the root-meanings “strong, firm, thick, fat” could have developed the meaning “pole” (the birch tree is very pole-like in

1 The comparison to Santa Claus is very apt because the dark celestial patch without stars near the north pole/above the north pole (according to what era back in time one is at) was thought of in many Eurasian and Amerindian cultures as the celestial smoke-hole at the top of the tent or at the top of the lodge or hut, the vent-hole/chimney through which the smoke escapes out into the air above: the smoke being likened to the soul/spirit escaping into a higher realm. Santa Claus and his close counterparts in the rest of European folklore preserve this ancient tradition, especially since Santa Claus was from the North Pole/the Axis Mundi.

2 These quoted paragraphs are from Christopher E. Johnsen’s online post “Observations in Eddic Astronomy: Nidhögg, Yggdrassils Ask, and the Swan Song of Cygnus [sic]”, at this url: [Germanic Astronomy \(germanicmythology.com\)](http://germanicmythology.com).

3 πέτρᾱ meaning “rock formation: cliff, ledge, cave, ridge; stone as a material (for buildings, statues, etc.)” and πέτρος meaning “rock, stone, boulder” were both of unknown etymology before my work, and they were not traced to any Indo-European root. R. S. P. Beekes thought that the words are probably of Non-IE origin. I’m sure he was very wrong about that.

4 See: [sǣng - Wiktionary, the free dictionary](http://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/sang).

appearance) and from there the North Pole/the Axis Mundi/the World Tree. And from the very ancient association of the World-Tree with the Northern Cross/Cygnus, developed the meaning “four”. And from “strong, firm, thick, fat” developed the meaning “rock, stone; rock formation; boulder”. And “thick” could easily refer to the thick resin/gum of the birch tree as well.

Compare Ancient Greek πέτρᾱ meaning “rock formation: cliff, ledge, cave, ridge; stone as a material (for buildings, statues, etc.)” and πέτρος meaning “rock, stone, boulder” to Ancient Greek (Boeotian dialect) πέτταρες meaning “four”: and Aeolic πέσυρες meaning “four” and πέσσυρες meaning “four”: the difference in form between these “four” words and the “rock, stone” words may be attributed to the fact that the “rock, stone” words πέτρᾱ and πέτρος are via a Non-Greek Pelasgian Pre-Greek IE language. Or maybe the “rock, stone” words are native to Greek, since we find in Ancient Greek that the “four” word developed these forms when used in combination: τετρα- / πετρα- (in the Boeotian dialect) / πετρο- (in the Thessalian dialect).

Ancient Greek πέλλα “stone” may not derive from an earlier **pelsā*⁵ but instead from an earlier **k^wella* (if no one has posited this before, and I haven’t confirmed that anyone else has), which would make πέλλα (**k^wella*) cognate with Apollo, since the theonym Apollo has been posited to be cognate with the Lydian theonym *Qldāns* /k^wlḏāns/ (the name of a Lydian deity probably corresponding to Apollo), if *Qldāns* /k^wlḏāns/ comes from an earlier /k^walyán-/ before palatalization, syncope, and the pre-Lydian sound change **y > d*⁶.

The name Apollo is considered to be attested in Hittite in the form Apaliunas: the Hittite form reflects an early form **Apeljōn*, which may also be surmised from the comparison of Cypriot Ἀπειλῶν with Doric Ἀπέλλων⁷. A Luwian etymology has been proposed for Hittite *Apaliunas* which could make Apollo “The One of Entrapment”, perhaps in the sense of “Hunter”⁸. Hesychius connects the name Apollo with the Doric ἀπέλλα (*apella*), which means “assembly”, so that Apollo would be the god of political life, and for ἀπέλλα Hesychius he also gives the definition σηκός (*sekos*), “pen, fold, as in a fenced-in enclosure for animals”, and there are other indications that originally one of the main functions of Apollo was as a god of flocks and herds.

ἀπέλλαι was an initiation family-festival dedicated to Apollo. Compare Laconian Ancient Greek ἀπελλάζω “to assemble”. This is what I’m getting at: the meanings “assembly/to assemble” comes from “to put together firmly”; the meaning “pen, fold, as in a fenced-in enclosure for animals”⁹ comes from “to put together, to enclose (as in closing the hand into a tight fist); to make tight, to make firm”. The meaning “stone” seen in πέλλα comes from “firm, dense, thick, fat”. Apollo and Apaliunas are cognate to Lydian *Qldāns* /k^wlḏāns/ from an earlier /k^walyán-/ , which I posit is cognate with **k^wel(l)*, “firm, dense, thick, fat” the source that I posit for Doric ἀπέλλα and πέλλα and ἀπέλλαι and ἀπελλάζω .

5 Which would make πέλλα cognate with Proto-Germanic **falīsz/*felzaz*, “rock, cliff”, et al.

6 For this proposal that Apollo is cognate with Lydian *Qldāns* /k^wlḏāns/ from an earlier /k^walyán-/ , see Melchert, Harold Craig (1994), *Anatolian Historical Phonology*.

7 Angel, John L.; Mellink, Machteld Johanna (1986). *Troy and the Trojan War: A Symposium Held at Bryn Mawr College, October 1984*. Bryn Mawr Commentaries. p. 42. ISBN 978-0-929524-59-7.

8 Immerwahr, Sara Anderson; Chapin, Anne Proctor (2004). *Charis: Essays in Honor of Sara A. Immerwahr*. Amer School of Classical. p. 254. ISBN 978-0-87661-533-1.

9 Many of these holding-pens/folds were four-walls (one of them a gate swinging open) arranged to make a square. This would also add to the development of the meaning “four”, besides the Cygnus constellation/the Northern Cross.

See my paper on the etymology of Hermes for details about why I posit that Apollo, Apaliunas and *Qldāns* (and any other variants in Greek and in other languages) was a name that had a lot of polysemy: meaning “Fattener (>Nourisher, Protector), Binder/Entrapper, Strangler (strangler of wolves that try to attack the flock)” at the same time, with all meanings coming from “fat, thick, dense, firm; to make firm, to press, to bind together so as to make firm”. This soon was also extended to refer to putting together words to make lines of poetry (Apollo as a god of poetry); and from Fattener, Nourisher came also Apollo not just as the god of flocks and herds, but also as a god of medicine and healing.

This **k^{wel}(l)*, “firm, dense, thick, fat” I think is very likely cognate to **k^{wetwóres}* as described above. If so, then the root-meaning of **k^{wetwóres}* was not “pointed, sharp” but instead “firm, dense, thick, fat”, and from there referring to the firm, dense, strong pole of the Axis Mundi/the World-Tree, and to the thick resin/gum of the birch tree, and to rocks and stones. The meaning “four” developed from the very ancient association of the World-Tree with the Northern Cross/Cygnus constellation, the Swan. Also interesting is PIE **k^{weyt-}* “white; to shine” since the birch tree has white bark and swans have white plumage. I would expect that **k^{weyt-}* “white; to shine” derives from the birch tree meaning, which is from “firm, dense, thick, fat”.

A.G. February 13th 2024.

Part 3: Dithurambos: δῖθῦράμβος

In 1936, a scholar whose surname is Brandenstein published a theory that Dithur (found in δῖθῦράμβος, which meant “a hymn of/to Dionysus” as well as being an epithet of Dionysus) meant “four” in a Pre-Greek language (with Dithur=“four” deriving from PIE **k^{wetwóres}*=“four”) and that “Dithurambos” meant “four-step” referring to the supposed four-step meter of the Dithyrambic verse, and the theory supposes that thriambos (θρῖάμβος) meant “three-step”. These “four-step” and “three-step” theories have been rejected by a number of scholars of Ancient Greek, including R.S.P. Beekes and Versnel (Versnel wrote a book published in 1970 on the etymologies of dithurambos and thriambos).

The scholars Arthur Pickard-Cambridge (author of the 1962 edition of *Dithyramb, Tragedy and Comedy*. Oxford : Clarendon Press 1962) and T. B. L. Webster (who put out a revised edition of the 1962 book in 1970), mention (pp. 8-9), like a scholar named Dodds before them, the suggested association with the words "dithrera" or "dithrepsa", apparently meaning "tomb", found in Phrygian tomb inscriptions.

In the next edition I will explain in more detail and with more evidence, but I will summarize here that Dionysus was very much associated with trees: see Dendrites, an epithet of Dionysus deriving from Anc. Greek dendron=“tree”; see Drualos, a name of Dionysus among the Paeonians which is cognate with Anc. Greek drus=“oak tree; tree”; a close counterpart of Dionysus is the Phrygian Attis who turned into a pine tree

and the resin excretions/secretions of pine trees are the tears and ichor of Attis; likewise the thyrsus of Dionysus, itself a pole/rod/staff, was often topped with pine cones, otherwise it was topped with grape clusters; the grapevine plant is itself very associated with the “thick pole” idea, since we find in Galician *cepa* meaning “trunk of a grapevine and the vine itself” and deriving from Latin *cippus*, “stake; post; gravestone, tombstone; menhir”.

The meanings “gravestone, tombstone; menhir” for *cippus* indicate that “dithrera” or “dithrepsa” mean “tombstone” or “tomb” in Phrygian tomb inscriptions, deriving, as I posit, from PIE **k^wetwóres*, “firm, thick, dense; stone; post, pole; pillar”; and I posit that *δῖθῦρᾶμβος* originally referred to Dionysus in his aspect as tree-god/pole-god, god of the World-Tree/Axis Mundi. The portion “- ᾶμβος” is likely only a suffix, as I will detail next time.

Since in Thracian languages, **k^wetwóres* gave rise to *ketri-* (in *Ketriporis*) and *katroso* (most likely meaning “stone” in the *Kjolmen-Moesian* inscription) and since we find *dithrera* and *dithrepsa* in Phrygian, which are most likely cognate: the strong indication is that *δῖθῦρᾶμβος* is from Phrygian/Brygian.

Further indications that I am correct to posit that **k^wetwóres* meant “stone; pole; axis mundi; birch tree (and various other trees)” are the words that can be traced back to reconstructed PIE **g^wesd-*, “dense, compact; pole of wood”, encountered in Proto-Slavic **g^wòzdъ* “dense woodland, holt,, thicket”¹⁰ and Proto-Slavic **g^wòzdъ* “wooden peg; nail; iron spike” via Proto-Balto-Slavic **g^wasdís*, **g^wasdwi[?]* (whence Old Church Slavonic *гвоздѣи* (*gvozdvi*)). Possibly cognate with Armenian *կոշտ* (*košt*, “hard, tough”) and with o-stem Proto-Celtic **bozdos* (whence Middle Irish *bot* “tail, penis”), [Welsh](#) *both* (“hub, nave”), and Proto-Germanic **kwastuz*, source of many Germanic words referring to a broom and other wooden poles and branches.

For the Welsh meanings “hub, nave”, see how in older English usage “hub” also referred to male animals (the “hub, penis” connection again)¹¹, and in surveying, a hub is a stake with a nail in it, used to mark a temporary point. In some other examples in IE languages, a hub is thought of as a peg. Besides that, a hub is a firm joint, and there again we see “firm, hard”.

Immediately cognate to English “hub” is English “hob”, which includes the meanings: “the hub of a wheel; a rounded peg; a male ferret”. My theory is that English “hub” and English “hob” (which are of unknown etymology and unknown origin) are cognate to Phrygian *Kubeleya* (many Germanic words with initial H, such as “hub” and “hob”, derive from a root with initial K), which I derive from *Kub* meaning either “pointed” leading to “to goad, to drive; the Axis Mundi which drives the rotation of the

10 See: [Reconstruction:Proto-Slavic/gvozďъ - Wiktionary, the free dictionary](#) .

11 [hub - Wiktionary, the free dictionary](#)

stars” or from Kub meaning “firm, dense, strong”. More likely from Kub=”pointed”, as indicated by certain horse and mare words beginning with Kub- /Kab- which are often thought to be cognate with Kybele, and which probably derive from “pointed” leading to “fast” leading to “horse”, as I will detail next time.

A.G. February 18th 2024